

On the Etymologies of Thriambos, Dithyrambos, Thridax/Throdax, Thrion/Thria, Thriae, Thrix, Tithumallos, Dionysos, Pupluns/Fufluns, Silenos and more

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Abstract

A work detailing new etymologies for Ancient Greek θρίδαξ (=“lettuce”), θριδακίνη (=“lettuce”), θρόδαξ (=“lettuce”), θρύδαξ (=“lettuce”), θίδραξ (=“lettuce”), θιδρακίνη (=“lettuce”), *θόδραξ (=“lettuce”), θοδράκιον (=“lettuce”), θρίων (=“fig-leaf”), θριώ (=“animal fat, lard, tallow”)¹, θρίαμβος (=“hymn to Dionysus”; “epithet of Dionysus”), διθύραμβος (=“dithyramb {a kind of song/lyric poetry whose subject was originally Dionysus}”; “a name of Dionysus”), τιθύμαλλος (=“the spurge plant, *Euphorbia peplus*”), Διώνυσος (=“Dionysos”), νύμφη/νύμφᾶ (many meanings, see discussion in this work); Phrygian *tetrakine* (=“lettuce”); Etruscan *Pupluns/Fufluns*, *Pupluna*; Latin *Populonia*, *populus*, *pupa/puppa*; and more; new etymologies which are very likely the first correct etymologies for these words and names.

Part 1

It has long been known that the Latin word for lettuce, *lactuca*, derives from *lactis*, the Latin word for milk, because the lettuce plant (as well as its wild predecessors, such as *Lactuca virosa*) ooze out/bleed out a milky white latex sap whenever a part of the plant is broken/torn off/cut off. In the previous two editions of this paper, I posited that the Ancient Greek words for lettuce (the ones specified in the Abstract section of this work, as well as later in this paragraph) derive from a Non-Greek language from the ancient PIE root **ser/*sreu*, “to flow”², which could have led to words meaning milk/juice/sap, and from there could have led to a word (or words, considering the variations as separate

1 The θριώ discussed in this work is the one which Hesychius defines as meaning λίπος (=“animal fat, lard, tallow”). The homonym words having the form θριώ will not be discussed, since they have different etymologies.

2 The Proto-Greek reflex/development of PIE **Sr-* was **Hr-*, leading to R-/Rh- in Ancient Greek. Pie **Sr-* could have remained *Sr-* in Thracian, though elsewhere in Thracian we find Στρήμων (Strēmōn), Στραῖος (*Straiōs*), both from PIE **ser/*sreu*; but that does not rule out *Sr-* forms from being Thracian as well: see how in the Baltic IE languages, they have both *Sr-* and *Str-* words derived from the **ser/*sreu* root, even within the same language as in these Lithuanian examples: sriaumė, straumuo, sraumuo. For the [s]/[th] variation, compare examples such as Ancient Greek θάλασσα (“sea”) vis-a-vis Ancient Greek σάλασσα (“sea”) and Latin Salacia (=a sea goddess).

words) for “lettuce”, and could have led to a number of other words found in Ancient Greek.

My updated conclusion is that PIE **ker-*, “to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat”³ is the source---via a Non-Greek Indo-European language---of the Thri-/Thru-/Thro- in the words θρίδαξ (“lettuce”), θριδακίνη (“lettuce”), θρόδαξ (“lettuce”), θρούδαξ (“lettuce”), θρίων (“fig-leaf”), θρίᾱ (“fig leaf, grape leaf”), Θρίᾱ (a region/deme of ancient Attica), Θριάσιον (=the Thriasian plain, where Thria is in Attica), thrix (“hair; bristly protrusions similar to hair”), θριῶ (“animal fat, lard, tallow”)⁴, and Θρίαμβος / θρίαμβος (=“an epithet of Dionysus”, and “a hymn to Dionysus”).

The ancient Athenians and the Eleusinians considered the Thriasian Plain the cradle of agriculture and the location where cereals were cultivated for the first time, under the guidance of Demeter. So when I derive Θρίᾱ (a region/deme of ancient Attica) and Θριάσιον (=the Thriasian plain, where Thria was in Attica) from PIE **ker-*, “to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat”, I have great back-up and reason for that.

For my derivation of Ancient Greek θρίξ (“hair”) from PIE **ker-*, “to grow”, think of how hair grows, and compare how Proto-Germanic **hēra* (“hair” and the source of the English word “hair”) has been posited to derive from PIE **ker-*/**keres*=“rough hair, bristle”.

For my derivation of θρίδαξ (“lettuce”), θριδακίνη (“lettuce”), θρόδαξ (“lettuce”) and θρούδαξ (“lettuce”) from PIE **ker-*, “to grow”, be aware that wild lettuce has very bristly stems and leaves, and prickly lettuce is known for the bristly prickles that line the edges and the prominent white midvein on the undersides of its dandelion-like leaves. *Lactuca quercina* is the species of wild lettuce found in Ancient Greece, and though for prickly lettuce so far archaeobotanical evidence in Greek archaeological contexts is scanty, uncarbonised seeds have been retrieved from a 7th-century BC deposit in a sanctuary of Hera on Samos. It is also described by Theophrastus. In mythology, Aphrodite is said to have laid Adonis in a lettuce bed, leading to the vegetable's association with food for the dead (compare another meaning of PIE **ker-*: “to nourish”).

The variations θίδραξ (“lettuce”), θιδρακίνη (“lettuce”), *θόδραξ (“lettuce”), θοδράκιον (“lettuce”), which have the R sound after the D sound, instead

3 For the explanation and evidence for all these meanings for PIE **ker-* and Pre-PIE **ker-*, see my paper on the etymology of Hermes.

4 The θριῶ discussed in this work is the one which Hesychius defines as meaning λίπος (“animal fat, lard, tallow”). The homonym words having the form θριῶ will not be discussed, since they have different etymologies.

of after the initial aspirated T (=θ) sound, arose either from a difficulty of pronouncing the original forms among some speakers, or, I think more likely, through a process which can be viewed as a verbal blending/verbal confounding, which I will detail later; a blending/confounding which in effect likely makes these variants capable of being derived from PIE **k^wetwóres*, but not from the meaning “four”, but rather from other meanings, as I will detail later in this edition.

My main theory is that the Ancient Greek word θρίον (=“fig-leaf”) and θρίᾱ (=“fig-leaf” and also “grape-leaf” according to Hesychius’ glossary) come from an earlier **k^rion* and **k^ria*, from PIE **k^rer-* “to grow, to nourish; to fatten; fat, thick, firm” via Pelasgian or Thracian or a Brygian/Phrygian language once spoken in Greece; **k^rion* and **k^ria* referring probably to the hair on fig leaves and on the underside of grape leaves (and grape leaves often look quite similar to fig leaves), explaining why the word doesn’t mean “leaf (in general)” but rather specifically fig leaves and grape leaves.

Though fig leaves are quite thick, grape leaves are thin, so I don’t think the thickness of fig leaves is the main motivation: the hair is more likely, also considering the word θρίξ =“hair”. For various reasons explained in this paper, I no longer think that θρίον and θρίᾱ derive from “to flow”, so I don’t think that θρίον and θρίᾱ refer to the milky white latex/sap that oozes out/bleeds out when a fig leaf is snapped off/broken/cut off/torn off from a fig tree: note that grape leaves do not exude such a sap/latex at all, as far as I remember. It is possible that the word was transferred from fig leaf to grape because of the similar appearance regardless of white latex sap, but I think the “hairy” link is the primary motivation.

My main reason for my previous theory from “to flow” was the fact that the 1940 LSJ claimed that Hesychius glossed an obscure word θριώ as meaning: λίπος (=“animal fat, lard, tallow”). But another source claims that the Hesychius manuscript there actually says δῆμος (meaning “people”), not λίπος. But even if the correct reading is λίπος, my new theory is that that meaning comes from “firm, thick, dense, fat”, from **k^riō*, from PIE **k^rer-*, “to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat”.

Hesychius also states that θριώ was also the name of a festival of Apollo. There is very little information out there these days about the festival of Apollo known as θριώ: probably no one these days knows at what time of year it took place, nor do I know. If this θριώ represents a syncopated inflection of Ancient Greek θερίζω (=“to reap”)⁵, then it would refer to the harvest time (late August/September, even going into early October); if instead this θριώ is the θριώ that means λίπος, then it would derive from PIE **k^rer-*, “to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat” and would have to do

⁵ There was a syncopated inflection/conjugation of θερίζω attested as θριώ : see modern dictionaries of Ancient Greek.

with the food-giving animals and plants made possible by the sun: the meat and the fat of the animals, the juice of plants and so on---and if this name of the festival was the $\Theta\rho\iota\acute{\omega}$ that means $\lambda\acute{\iota}\pi\omicron\varsigma$, then the festival probably also involved the offering of animal fat and perhaps some juices/plant-derived oils/portions of milk etc. to Apollo, and it could have taken place well-before harvest time (of course, not all plant-produced foods are harvested at the same time of year), in the spring for example.

I think that the $\Theta\rho\iota$ - found in $\Theta\rho\iota\acute{\alpha}\mu\beta\omicron\varsigma$ derives from this same $*\acute{k}ri$ - stem deriving from PIE $*\acute{k}er$. “to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat”.

That PIE root fits Dionysus very well because Dionysus was a god of the fertility of plants and their burgeoning in the spring-time; and a god who was associated with fertility in general, and with the richness and food and drink that comes from nature⁶.

So my conclusion is $\Theta\rho\iota\acute{\alpha}\mu\beta\omicron\varsigma$ etymologically does not reference the inspired/rapt/possessed flowing out of words, even though in practice in actuality, the $\Theta\rho\iota\acute{\alpha}\mu\beta\omicron\varsigma$ became associated with that, and Thriambic hymns, like Dithyrambic hymns, were apparently often uttered impromptu spontaneously, so they often were an “inspired/rapt/possessed flowing out of words”---very parallel to the twittering of birds in the spring-time.

From the earlier meanings of $\Theta\rho\iota\acute{\alpha}\mu\beta\omicron\varsigma$ (“Fattener, Nourisher; the Growing One, the Fat one, the Firm One; the thick firm growing Tree-Pole” since Dionysus was very much a god of trees) as a name/epithet of the god, $\theta\rho\iota\acute{\alpha}\mu\beta\omicron\varsigma$ came to mean a Dionysiac song/hymn, Dionysiac poetry.

I no longer (as I did in the Autumn and Winter of 2022, and for sometime afterwards) think that the Thri- of Thriambos derives from Sri- in turn from PIE $*sreu/*ser$, “to flow” (since Dionysus was the god of wine, positing the principal meaning “to flow” was attractive, but my new theory works much better). And even if Thriambos did derive from PIE $*sreu/*ser$, there is no indication that a derivation from that root would mean that Thriambos would also have the meanings “noisy” in reference to flowing water; or would have the meanings “murmuring, purling’ etc. in reference to the sounds of rushing and/or flowing water.

Nor is there a clear indication that PIE $*sreu/*ser$, “to flow” arose as a word imitative of the rushing sounds of flowing water; I was thinking that that was probably the origin of PIE $*sreu/*ser$, “to flow”, and that the rushing/flowing sound in this case was conceived of as harsh and strident, and that it was also likely applied to “hard” (“hard” developing in this case from “harsh” sounds) things such as tree trunks; these theories from the second edition of this paper are possible, but it seems that none of the words that I am discussing in this paper actually derive from PIE $*sreu/*ser$, “to flow”.

⁶ And see also how among the Etruscans, their Dionysus equivalent (Pupluns/Fufluns) was a god of plant life, happiness, wine, health, and growth in all things.

My updated theory, even more so than the theory in the second version of this paper, is very different from H.S. Versnel's conclusion in his extensively researched and scholarly work⁷ wherein he concluded that Thri- only⁸ meant "to shout, yell": while "to shout, yell" was at least one of the meanings of Bacchus, Iacchus, Bromios and a few other Dionysian epithets, there's no compelling indication that Θρίαμβος meant "to yell/to shout".

One may ask, how does my updated theory explain the Ancient Greek word θριάζω="to be rapt, possessed"? That could be from Θριαί, nymphs who were associated with growth and nourishment and with the fatness of spring, and also with prophesying: with oracular, inspired utterances, often given in a trance-state by priestesses. The Ancient Greek author Philochorus (FGrHist 328FI95) in fact stated that the word thriasthai (=prophesying) derives from Θριαί: "nymphs that inhabited Parnassos, the nurses of Apollo, three, called Thriai, after whom the mantic pebbles are called thriai and prophesying, thriasthai."

My previous theory was that θριάζω ("to be rapt, possessed") derives from "to flow; flowing"; I no longer think that that is the case, but even that former theory of mine was closer to the truth than Versnel's theory that Thriambos meant "yelling, shouting": because "to be rapt, possessed" is much more like a flowing out words, as when an oracle extemporated verbal expressions/phrases or as when a Dionysiacally- enthused person extemporated poetry and verbal expressions.

The Ancient Greek term θριαί, of undetermined etymology in the linguistic literature, referred to two things: 1) pebbles that were thrown for divination purposes 2) and, properly capitalized, Θριαί referred to three nymphs who resided on Mount Parnassos and who were directly associated with the throwing of mantic pebbles for divination purposes: the main source for this is Philochorus (FGrHist 328FI95), "nymphs who inhabited Parnassos, the nurses of Apollo, three, called Thriai, after whom the mantic pebbles are called thriai and prophesying, thriasthai."

7 H.S. Versnel's *Triumphus: An inquiry into the origin, development and meaning of the Roman triumph*. Leiden, E.J. Brill, 1970. This work is must-reading (as is my work here) for an understanding of what is known and for much of what (before my work) could have been said about the etymologies of θρίαμβος and διθύραμβος: his work includes a history of the etymological attempts and the history of the linguistic analysis and classical scholarship, as well as the original attestations in Ancient Greek and analysis of the Ancient Greek usage of the words.

8 It did not occur to Versnel that Thri- could be from PIE *k^{er} . "to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat" or from PIE *ser/*sreu "to flow", so I don't mean that Versnel was excluding those ideas, he just didn't think of them. I have seen no Ancient Greek words that suggest Versnel's theory for thriambos. But I will mention in this note Ancient Greek στρίξ="owl (the screech owl more than any others?)", which referred to the sounds of owls and/or to the screeching of screech owls specifically; so one can infer a root-meaning of "calling out/yelling/screeching/shouting" in Ancient Greek, which is rather certain even though that's not attested in Ancient Greek. Rather certain for a number of reasons, and one reason is because that meaning is found in Romanian, where *a striga* means "to call for someone; shout; yell", deriving from Latin strix=a screech owl, from Ancient Greek στρίξ="owl". Versnel does not mention "strix" in his work, and there is no reason to think that στρίξ is cognate to thriambos. And Ancient Greek τρίζω (= "to squeak, creak") is more like the twittering/chirping of birds than a shout/yell, a twittering/chirping that flows out profusely.

These Θριαί have been further described as “a trio of sisters personifying the mantic pebbles used at Delphi”⁹. From Philochorus’ quote, it’s quite certain that at Delphi (and very likely also at some other sites) the pebble-throwing was done in association with oracular word-flows uttered by inspired/rapt/possessed persons (priestesses at Delphi). But it’s to be expected that aside from such oracular priestesses (and priests?) many common people would attempt some type of divination by throwing pebbles in such a manner, but without any verbal utterances to accompany the pebble-tossing¹⁰.

Though yelling/shouting was a big part of Dionysiac rites, as we can see this Θριαί word most likely did not have any connotation of “shouting, yelling”.

Philochorus’ may have been right that Θριαί used for those mantic pebbles derives from Θριαί, the three nymphs of Parnassos, one of whose functions was performing divination: by tossing pebbles, by interpreting bird omens, and likely via other means as well. But from where does Θριαί derive? Probably from PIE **ker*. “to grow, to nourish, to fatten; thick, firm, fat”: for a number of reasons, including the fact that the Θριαί were nurses of Apollo who would have nourished him with their honey, as a Melissa nymph in some traditions nourished the baby Zeus.

It’s unclear/unknown whether the Thriai were originally three nymphs or whether instead, folk etymology identifying Thri- with Tri- (Tri- meaning “three” in Ancient Greek) gave rise to the conception that there were three Thriai nymphs; there seems to have been a rarely occurring Thri- stem meaning “three” in Ancient Greek (probably from a Non-Greek language), see in particular θρῖναξ=trident.

It has been disputed by at least two scholars¹¹ whether the Θριαί and the three Bee-Maiden nymphs of the Homeric Hymn to Hermes are the same; the scholar S. Scheinberg avers that there is no confirmation that the Thriae have anything to do with either bees or Hermes, and that the Thriae can only be confirmed to be associated with Apollo; she points out that the Hymn mentions nothing about mantic pebbles, the main attribute of the Thriae; but the hymn does specify that the three Bee Nymph Maidens were also teachers of divination and performers of divination. In my opinion, the correct scholars in this case are those who believe that the Thriae are the same as the three Bee Nymph Maidens discussed in the Homeric Hymn to Hermes; like the Thriae, the three

9 This quote describing the Thriai like this is from the February 1996 paper: *The Corycian Nymphs and the Bee Maidens of the Homeric Hymn to Hermes*, by Jennifer Larson of Kent State University, in *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies*: pp. 341–357.

10 Such is the conclusion in *The Corycian Nymphs and the Bee Maidens of the Homeric Hymn to Hermes*, by Jennifer Larson of Kent State University, in *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies*: pp. 341–357. February 1996.

11 S. Scheinberg in 1979 and Jennifer Larson in 1996.

Bee Nymph Maidens were also stated to reside on Mount Parnassos, and there are a number of other coincidings which speak to their identity.

The Bee Maiden Nymphs/the Thriae were depicted in some Ancient Greek artworks as half-woman/half-bee nymphs, but usually shown with bird-wings, not bee-wings; and I find them to be similar to the three Norns of Norse myth (who were closely associated with swans, but not with bees) and to the three Graeae of Ancient Greek myth, whom Aeschylus described as having swan-shaped bodies: swans were associated with far north (because of their migration patterns; because of their white plumage; because of the Cygnus constellation, which also known as the Northern Cross), and the far north was the usual location for the Axis Mundi/World Tree, usually identified with the North Pole; and the Cygnus constellation/Northern Cross was from very ancient times was directly linked with the Axis Mundi/World Tree/North Pole. Besides the ash tree, northern Eurasian people often thought of the World-Tree as being a birch tree: and in IE languages and Non-IE languages, words often shift in meaning from birch tree to ash tree, and from ash tree to birch tree. The birch tree has a very pole-like shape to its trunk, as does the ash tree and many other trees.

The Norns were associated with the Ash tree as the world-tree of Norse myth, while the Manna Ash tree (*Fraxinus ornus*) found in Southern Europe secretes a sweet edible substance, hence the term “Manna Ash tree”: the sweet edible substance is likened to Manna. In an Ancient Greek myth, méli (honey) drips from the Manna ash (*Fraxinus ornus*), with which the Meliae (“honey nymphs” and/or “Manna Ash tree nymphs” since the Ancient Greek word for the Manna Ash tree is *Melia*, deriving from méli “honey” because of the sweet secretion of the tree) nursed the infant god Zeus on the island of Crete (as in the Hymn to Zeus by Callimachus).

It’s likely than in more ancient, pre-Classical times, for example in Neolithic times and further back, the bee-nymphs/bee-maidens were identified with the swan-nymphs/swan-maidens, the crane-nymphs, the partridge-nymphs, the dove-nymphs---with certain birds whose qualities fall into the proper niche in relation to the Bee-Maidens---but a number of factors such as the often sinister connotation of half-bird/half-human figures in Greek mythology favored the half-bee representation, and bees are more directly linked to the process of spring-time than birds are, and the “cult” of the Bee-Maidens and their divine and inspiring honey was a very old cult: conceiving of the Bee nymphs as birds would not work, so the bird aspects were pushed aside and separated out into different orders of nymphs and other supernatural creatures.

I have found that many ancient European gods and goddesses were closely associated and identified with the World-Tree. And Dionysus---who was in large part a

tree-god (see for example *Dendrites* as an epithet of Dionysus, from Ancient Greek “dendron”=“tree”) was surely identified with the World-Tree.

And since bees so often have their hives in trees, and since the Thriae seem to have been closely associated with the springtime, and Dionysus was the god of Springtime---then most likely the famed Classical scholar Jane Harrison was correct in positing in 1908 that the Thriae would have been nurses of Dionysus ¹² in some now-lost ancient Greek or Brygian or Thracian or Pelasgian tradition. These Bee Maiden nymphs were embodiments of/spirits overseeing the flowing juices and saps and resins and honey of spring-time; and I think the sweet grape juice would come within their sphere, so similar to honey.

Springtime: full of the twittering of birds, the buzzing of bees: it is interesting that Thriae is similar to the Ancient Greek word θρῦλος / θρύλλος =”noise as of many voices; murmur” and to the Ancient Greek word θόρυβος =”noise, especially of a crowd of people; uproar; clamor; tumult, confusion, trouble”; and the reduplicated form τονθορούζω =”to mumble”; so I posit as a second theory that Thriae may have meant “buzzing, murmuring, mumbling” and encompassing oracular utterances as well. Again we see the connection of the word Thriambos to the buzzing of bees and to oracular murmurings, but not to yelling; and why would half-bee nymphs be associated with shouting and yelling? Bees can be loud, but no, there’s no evidence that the Thriae were shouters: instead they buzzed and murmured. I don’t recall whether Versnel claims that the Thriae were shouters, or whether he even discusses the Thriae in his work on thriambos.

The 10th century AD/CE Suidas Greek lexicon writes: “they call the madness of poets Thriasis”: the madness of poets is not a yelling and a shouting kind of madness. And the Suidas also suggests connection with Thria (fig leaves and grape leaves) as I do.

Earlier I stated that I would detail what word(s) could have caused θρίδαξ to become the variant form θίδραξ; and θρόδαξ to become the variant *θόδραξ/θοδράκιον, and could have caused the Phrygian form *tetrakine* as well: words derived from a PIE root **k^wetwóres* “firm, thick, dense; pole; stone; wood; to fatten, to nourish, to make strong; to grow” probably are responsible for the θίδραξ, *θόδραξ/θοδράκιον and Phrygian *tetrakine* forms. I will discuss the root **k^wetwóres* “firm, thick, dense; pole; stone; wood; to fatten, to nourish, to make strong, to grow” in detail in Part 2 of this paper. Since those lettuce words likely derive from “to grow” in reference to the bristles on the stems of wild lettuce and on prickly lettuce, as discussed

12 See pages 441 to 443 of Jane Harrison’s 1908 classic study of Ancient Greek religion/mythology, *Prolegomena to the study of Greek religion*, a book that I have owned since 2003 or 2002.

earlier; and since I posit that the PIE root **k^wetwóres* included the meaning “to grow”: it becomes likely.

The Phrygian form tetrakine shows a de-aspiration of the T sound: from Th to T; and a shift of the vowel to the E vowel, not seen in Ancient Greek. Note that the Phrygian word for “four” is claimed to have been θιδρα- in some sources, which would be nearly identical to θίδραξ, which is one of the forms of the lettuce word in Ancient Greek.

One may ask, if θιδρα- was the Phrygian word for “four”---and if it was it would of course derive from PIE **k^wetwóres* “four”---why do we find Tetra- in tetrakine if that Tetra- also derives from PIE **k^wetwóres*, but from the meaning “to grow”? Good question, but the different forms may have an explanation within the scenario that they are cognates.

Alternatively, the Ancient Greek word θέω (“I run (fast); I fly”) could possibly have caused the shift from Thrid-/Thrud-/Throd- to Thidr-, *Thudr-, Thodr-, since the way that white latex sap flows out of lettuce and wild lettuce could have caused an association with θέω=“to flow”.

We find that the Ancient Greek male/masculine name Θόᾱς¹³ derives from θέω. Since Θόᾱς begins with Tho-, as does *Thodrax/Thodrak-, I find this scenario quite likely. And the shift from Thri- to Thi- seen in θίδραξ could also have been caused by θέω. The Ancient Greek word θέω (“I run (fast); I fly”) derives from PIE **d^hew-* “to run, flow” (which in turn I posit derives from *d^h*=“force”, with “force” leading to “run”, which led to “flow”; I explain this in more detail in another work of mine). Another Ancient Greek word that could have influenced the shift is Ancient Greek θορός/θορή “semen, sperm”, from PIE **d^herh₃-*, “to leap, spring”¹⁴.

Another Ancient Greek word (of Pre-Greek or Brygian origin, most likely) that could have influenced the shift is *Dithur-*, which is most likely from the root-form **k^wetwóres*---but it certainly didn’t mean “four”. In part 2, I will detail my new etymology of Dithurambos, and I will also detail that -αμβος found in Thriambos and Dithurambos and Iambos, etc., is most likely just a suffix.

13 Θόᾱς was also an alternative ancient name (still masculine/male) of the river Ἀχελῷος: in this case as probably in all cases, the name Θόᾱς meant “Fast/Swift”, referring to the speed of the river’s flow. It’s possible that Ἀχελῷος likewise meant “swift, fast”, and this could also be the meaning of the name Ἀχιλλεύς (Achilles): “swift, fast”. In the newer editions of my work on the translation of the Thracian Ezerovo ring, I published my theory that Ἀχελῷος meant “white, bright” (referring to the color of the river’s water: see other names for the Achelous river which do refer to the river as a white river) and that Ἀχιλλεύς meant “bright; radiant” or “spear(-man)” or “striker/slayer” or all those meanings at the same time, with all those possible meanings for Achilles developing from an ancient root-word whose oldest meaning was “pointed”. In those editions, I was going to add that “pointed” sometimes also leads to “fast, swift”. Alternatively, the meanings “fast, swift” could derive from a different root-meaning.

14 For this etymology of θορός/θορή, see Beekes (2010).

Part 2

Aeschylus wrote of the Dithyrambos: “it is fitting that the dithyramb of diverse utterance should accompany Dionysus, but the ordered Paeon and the sober Muse should attend Apollo”. *Diverse utterance*=free-verse, free-flowing, not set to a four-step meter.

My conclusion and the conclusion of numerous scholars and linguists is that Dithyrambos did not mean “four-step meter”, a notion based on the fallacy that “thriambos” meant “three-step meter”.

See also in Plato’s Phaedrus where Plato is narrating what Socrates is saying when Socrates visited a place sacred to nymphs: here are Socrates’ words (or Plato’s words, if invented by Plato; or Socrates modified by Plato) translated into English from Ancient Greek:

“The place seems to be really divine, so that you need not be surprised if in the course of my speech I am subject to recurrent attacks of nympholepsy¹⁵. Just now my utterance nearly broke into dithyrambics” (Plato, Phaedrus, 258c—d).

Borgeaud¹⁶ comments: “For Plato, as we know, inspiration is a form of disassociation whereby the speaker is no longer responsible for what he says”. The conclusion is Dithyramb did not mean “four-step meter”, a notion based on the fallacy that “thriambos” meant “three-step meter”, but it did not. To think that all suddenly inspired verse/utterances came out in four-step meter is far-fetched.

I expect that dithyrambic utterances had varying meter: the core idea was the spontaneity and the sudden flowing out of words, which came out in various rhythms. Next time I will include some more quotes to show this.

One can imagine a scenario of an inspired person suddenly expressing lines that all come in four-step meter as if some supernatural being had already composed them and simply speaks through the person, but why suppose four-step meter in the first place? Just because some linguist in the 1930s came up with the superficial idea (based on Thri- resembling Tri=Three) that Thriambos means

15 Nympholepsy=“possessed by nymphs” or “taken by nymphs”, which can cause dithyrambic free-verse speech.

16 Philippe Borgeaud, *The Cult of Pan in Ancient Greece*, English translation.

“three-step”, then from there Dithyrambos means “four-step”? No, most likely they were talking about a kind of spontaneous free-verse of varying rhythms.

I have found that the διθύρ- in the Ancient Greek word διθύραμβος (= “dithyramb {a kind of song/lyric poetry whose subject was originally Dionysus}”; “a name of Dionysus”) most likely does derive from PIE **k^wetwóres* , but not from the meaning “four”, but instead from a Pre-PIE/PIE **k^wetwóres* meaning “firm, thick, dense; pole; stone; wood; to fatten, to nourish, to make strong; to grow”.

If this is correct, the meaning of διθύραμβος was about the same as that of θρίαμβος : which is not surprising since both terms have the same dictionary definitions: 1) an epithet/name of Dionysus 2) a song/hymn about Dionysus.

In 1936, a scholar whose surname is Brandenstein published a theory that Dithur (found in διθύρᾶμβος , which meant “a hymn of/to Dionysus” as well as being an epithet of Dionysus) meant “four” in a Pre-Greek language (with Dithur=“four” deriving from PIE **k^wetwóres*=“four”) and that “Dithurambos” meant “four-step” referring to the supposed four-step meter of the Dithyrambic verse, and the theory supposes that thriambos (θρίαμβος) meant “three-step”. These “four-step” and “three-step” theories have been rejected by a number of scholars of Ancient Greek, including R.S.P. Beekes and Versnel (Versnel wrote a book published in 1970 on the etymologies of dithurambos and thriambos).

The scholars Arthur Pickard-Cambridge (author of the 1962 edition of *Dithyramb, Tragedy and Comedy*. Oxford : Clarendon Press 1962) and T. B. L. Webster (who put out a revised edition of the 1962 book in 1970), mention (pp. 8-9), as does a scholar named Dodds before them, the suggested association with the words "dithrera" or "dithrepsa", apparently meaning "tomb", found in Phrygian tomb inscriptions.

In the next edition I will explain in more detail and with more evidence, but I will summarize here that Dionysus was very much associated with trees: see Dendrites, an epithet of Dionysus deriving from Anc. Greek dendron=“tree”; see Drualos, a name of Dionysus among the Paeonians which is cognate with Anc. Greek drus=“oak tree; tree”; a close counterpart of Dionysus is the Phrygian Attis who turned into a pine tree and the resin excretions/secretions of pine trees are the tears and ichor of Attis; likewise the thyrsus of Dionysus, itself a pole/rod/staff, was often topped with pine cones, otherwise it was topped with grape clusters; the grapevine plant is itself very associated with the “thick pole” idea, since we find in Galician cepa meaning “trunk of a grapevine

and the vine itself” and deriving from Latin cippus, “stake; post; gravestone, tombstone; menhir”.

The meanings “gravestone, tombstone; menhir” for cippus indicate that "dithrera" or "dithrepsa" mean "tombstone" or “tomb” in Phrygian tomb inscriptions, deriving, as I posit, from PIE **k^wetwóres*, “firm, thick, dense; stone; post, pole; pillar”; and I posit that *διθύρᾱμβος* originally referred to Dionysus in his aspect as tree-god/pole-god, god of the World-Tree/Axis Mundi. The portion “- ᾱμβος “ is likely only a suffix, as I will detail more next time.

Since in Thracian languages, **k^wetwóres* gave rise to ketri- (in Ketriporis) and katroso (most likely meaning “stone” in the Kjolmen-Moesian inscription) and since we find dithrera and dithrepsa in Phrygian, which are most likely cognate: the rather strong indication is that *διθύρᾱμβος* is from Phrygian/Brygian.

Further indications that I am correct to posit that **k^wetwóres* meant “stone; pole; axis mundi; birch tree (and various other trees)” are the words that can be traced back to reconstructed PIE **gwesd-*, “dense, compact; pole of wood”, encountered in Proto-Slavic **gvòzdъ* “dense woodland, holt,, thicket”¹⁷ and Proto-Slavic **gvòzdъ* “wooden peg; nail; iron spike” via Proto-Balto-Slavic **gwasdís*, **gwasdwī*² (whence Old Church Slavonic *гвоздьи* (*gvozdvi*)). Possibly cognate with Armenian *կոշտ* (*košt*, “hard, tough”) and with o-stem Proto-Celtic **bozdos* (whence Middle Irish *bot* “tail, penis”), Welsh *both* (“hub, nave”), and Proto-Germanic **kwastuz*, source of many Germanic words referring to a broom and other wooden poles and branches.

For the Welsh meanings “hub, nave”, see how in older English usage “hub” also referred to male animals (the “hub, penis” connection again)¹⁸, and in surveying, a hub is a stake with a nail in it, used to mark a temporary point. In some other examples in IE languages, a hub is thought of as a peg. Besides that, a hub is a firm joint, and there again we see “firm, hard”.

Immediately cognate to English “hub” is English “hob”, which includes the meanings: “the hub of a wheel; a rounded peg; a male ferret”. My theory is that English “hub” and English “hob” (which are of unknown etymology and unknown origin) are cognate to Phrygian Kubeleya (many Germanic words with initial H, such as “hub” and “hob”, derive from a root with initial K), which I derive from Kub meaning either “pointed” leading to “to goad, to drive; the Axis Mundi which drives the rotation of the stars” or from Kub meaning “firm, dense, strong”. More likely from Kub=“pointed”, as indicated by certain horse and mare words beginning with Kub- /Kab- which are often thought to be cognate with Kubele, and which probably derive from “pointed” leading to “fast” leading to “horse”, as I will detail next time.

17 See: [Reconstruction:Proto-Slavic/gvozдь - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](#) .

18 [hub - Wiktionary, the free dictionary](#)

Both Dithu- and Thri- are suffixed with -αμβος; why? Did -αμβος mean “song” deriving from -αμβος meaning “sound/loud song”¹⁹ as Versnel posited?

Versnel argues that in Ancient Greek, -μβος was often used to enhance words that convey sound (see Versnel, page 33), so -ambos might have been used to connect Thri- and Dithu- with sound, because on their own Thri- and Dithu- (according to my conclusions in this edition) have nothing to do with sound (though the Thri- in Thriae might have to do with buzzing and murmuring as described earlier). But if attached to -ambos (If -ambos meant “song; noise”) they became unambiguous sound-conveying words.

As I will detail next time though, it is more likely that -αμβος in Dithurambos and Thriambos and Iambos is just a suffix.

The Ancient Greek word(s) τῖθῦμᾶλλος/τῖθῦμᾶλος/τῖθῦμᾶλλίς referred to several closely-related plants: 1) the spurge plant, *Euphorbia peplus* 2) the sea-spurge, *Euphorbia paralias* 3) the sun-spurge plant, *Euphorbia helioscopia*, which was also called in Ancient Greek Ἡλιοσκόπιος=“looking to the sun”; and some other spurge species.

The Tithu- of these words is not cognate to Dithur- and I interpret the word(s) like so: τῖθῦ=“sun; bright” in Pre-Greek, as we find in the theonym Τιθωνός, a god of the dawn; and Ancient Greek *titō* =“day, sun”. See also τῖτᾶνος /τέτᾶνος =“a kind of white earth, probably gypsum; chalk, lime”.

while μᾶλλος=“looking; to look” in Pre-Greek, probably from a root that meant “bright; white” as we see for example with the etymology of English “look” from PIE *lewk=“bright; white; light; to see”. See Ancient Greek μᾶλος=“white” attested in Theocritus, and see Ancient Greek μᾶλλός “wool” of undetermined etymology, likely Pre-Greek.

19 I don’t think that αμβος meant “grape/grapevine” in Thriambos and Dithurambos, though I mentioned that theory (a theory also deriving from my work) in the second edition of this paper, in December 2022 and in another work from Autumn of 2022, where I first posited that αμβος could have meant “grape/grapevine”, because of Ancient Greek ἄμπελος/ἀμπέλος (=“vine, grapevine”). See also Albanian âmbël/amël/ëmbël=“sweet” and Dacian amolusta=“chamomile” and Dutch amper=“sour”.

Procopius mentions an “Illyrian” name variously rendered (in different manuscripts, or different secondary sources) as Dithubistos or Ditubistos or Dithubista/Ditubista: for the ending part *bista*+/bistos, there is also attested the Thracian name *Aulobista* (composed of the well-known Daco-Thracian name Aulo²⁰ plus the termination *bista*²¹) and the Dacian name Burebista (variants include Boirebista, Boirebostes, Buruista, etc.): but my conclusion is that the Ditu-/Dithu- of these Illyro-Thracian names (a Ditu/Dithu found in some other Thracian names as well) is not cognate to the Dithur- of Dithurambos and instead Ditu/Dithu might be cognate to the Tithu- of Tithumallos/Tithumalos/Tithumallis, with a meaning of “bright, light, sun, dawn”.

Part 3----Dionysus

I may have uncovered the actual etymology of the Nysos part of Dionysus (Διόνυσος) as well: the etymology of the Dio/Διό part is already known: that is from PIE **dyew-* “to be bright; sky, heaven”. The Nysos part probably meant “to sprout, rise”, explaining why Νῦσα (=Nysa/Nusa) was the name of a number of mountains in Ancient Greece (in later myths at least, Dionysus was said to have been born on one such mountain named Νῦσα).

This interpretation of mine ties in with an interpretation for Nysos found as far back as 1890, when P. Kretschmer postulated that Nysos means “son” and Dionysos means “Son of Zeus”: it is extremely common for a word meaning “to sprout” to develop into a word meaning “offspring, child” (see for example Ancient Greek ἔρνος=“young shoot; sprout; scion; offspring”); so while I don’t think that “Son of Zeus” was the only meaning of Dionysos, it likely was one of the meanings. Kretschmer was not thinking of a word meaning “to sprout; sprout; spring; rise”, that did not occur to him, so his thesis was too limited and off-target.

My interpretation would explain the attestation of νύσα=δένδρον (*déndron*) =”a tree”, and trees sprout up and often rise up high: for example, the Latin words *arbor/arbōs* (=”tree”) and *arduus* (=”lofty, high, steep”) are both thought to derive from PIE **h₃erd^h-* “to increase, grow; upright; high”,

20 I think the Thracian name Aulo meant “firm, remaining in place, surviving, victorious”, from **h₂ews-*, in turn from PIE **h₂wes-* by Schwebeablaut, as is the case for Ancient Greek αὐλή.

21 The suffixed element *bista(s)/bostes* might have meant “sprout, offshoot” and maybe also “offspring, child”, and if so, the root would be PIE **weys-*, “to raise, increase; to procreate, produce”: compare Lithuanian *visti*=”to multiply, breed”, derived from PIE **weys-*.

The Ancient Greek words *νύσσα* (=a post, for example a turning-post used in races) and *νύσσω* (=touch with a sharp point, prick, stab, pierce; nudge; sting; impinge upon) are surely cognates to the *Νῦσα* mountain-names: the verb *νύσσω* looks like it derives from “something pointed”, which is sometimes allied with “to sprout”, and “to sprout” is always allied with “to rise”. So I find it most likely that *Διόνυσος* /Dionysos implied primarily “God of sproutings”, which works extremely well for him. An epithet of Dionysos was *Dendrites* (=“of the trees”), and considering that attestation where *νύσα*=*δένδρον* (*déndron*), “a tree”, that’s quite interesting. Among the Paeonians, Dionysus was called *Drualos*, where *Dru*=“tree, oak tree”.

It may be that *Nus/Nuss* meant “pointed; to prick, to goad” and “to prick, to goad” can lead to “to cause to sprout (as if goaded into sprouting)” and “to prick, to goad” can lead to “to inspire” and to “to madden” and to “to enrage”. Other times, “pointed” and “to sprout” are allied by the fact that a sprout first breaks the soil as a little point emerging from the ground.

Or it may be that the meanings of *νύσσα* (=a post, for example a turning-post used in races) are older and derive from “firm, thick, fat; to fatten, to nourish”, and the meanings of *νύσσω* (=touch with a sharp point, prick, stab, pierce; nudge; sting; impinge upon) derive from the meaning “to jab/poke/stick with a stick”, in turn from “stick, stake”, which came from “stake, pole; firm, thick, etc.” as described above.

The Ancient Greek word *νύμφη/νύμφᾶ*²² (*númphē/númphā*) quite likely represents what is known as a chiming root vis-a-vis *νύσα/νύσσα*: looking at/studying the definitions of *νύμφη/νύμφᾶ* in Ancient Greek, they--*numph* and *nus(s)*²³---do seem to be chiming roots: which means they are root-words of very similar sonic/verbal form and in this case a nearly identical or identical semantic range. Consider the various Ancient Greek meanings of *νύμφη/νύμφᾶ*:

- 1) “young nubile woman, marriageable maiden; young girl”, from where developed the meanings “bride, young wife”;
- 2) “a goddess of lower rank, often goddesses of various water-springs”: poetically at least the word also meant “spring; spring water”;
- 3) “doll, puppet” (this meaning derives from “little girl” and from “little young creature”, even though dolls and puppets are not living creatures, but they are representations of such);
- 4) “bee or wasp in pupa stage”
- 5) “winged male ant”
- 6) “a kind of mollusk”
- 7) “point of a plowshare”

22 *νύμφᾶ* (*númphā*) is the Doric Greek form.

23 I compare also Etruscan *nurph*=“nine”, since I have found that the PIE root for “nine”: PIE **h₁néwǵ*, “nine”: most likely derives from a root-meaning “to sprout”, because it usually takes human women nine months to give birth, so very likely “nine” derives from a root-word meaning “to sprout”, a root-word which is quite certainly PIE **néwos*, “new, fresh” (see my work on the etymology of *Hera* for a detailed discussion of that: that’s where I first published that theory; that work is also available on Zenodo). So quite interesting that the Etruscan word for “nine” is *nurph*, which looks a lot like *numph*- in Ancient Greek.

- 8) “hollow between the lower lip and the chin”
- 9) “depression on the shoulder of a horse”
- 10) “opening rosebud” (and other flower buds)
- 11) “clitoris, also the labia minora”
- 12) “niche”.

I have seen pretty much identical semantic sets before: the root-meaning was “to sprout; something that sprouts; something pointed”; “sprout” led to “tender young living creature”, which explains: young girl, young nubile woman, marriageable maiden, and any meanings that proceed from there; “tender young living creature” also explains “bee or wasp in pupa stage” and “winged male ant”, and I’m pretty sure the word also applied to winged female ants, which often look identical to winged male ants: both male and female winged ants are young, fresh ants that sprout up/pour out from the ground in large numbers and take wing: reminiscent also of water springing up from the ground: and the root-meaning “to sprout” also explains the emphasis on water-springs and the word being used for fresh water-springs; “a kind of mollusk” most likely derives from the “tender, soft living creature” meaning, here used regardless of youth it seems, but maybe not regardless of youth; my explanation also explains “opening rosebud (and other flower buds)”; also explains the clitoris meaning: the clitoris is a tender sprout;

the meaning “point of a plowshare” shows one of the oldest meanings of the set, that is to say “something pointed”: and “something pointed” led to “hollow between the lower lip and the chin, little depressions (the depression on a shoulder of a horse referred to is a small depression that sometimes is found there on horses, these days often called a “prophet’s thumbprint”), niches”: as is often observed (see also $\nu\acute{\sigma}\sigma\omega$ =touch with a sharp point, prick, stab, pierce; nudge; sting; impinge upon) such meanings often derive from “something pointed”, since they look like they were made by something pointed: and also the hollow between the lower lip and the chin is soft/tender, and “soft/tender” is a major meaning that developed from “sprout”.

So with $\nu\acute{\mu}\phi\eta/\nu\acute{\mu}\phi\bar{\alpha}$, we see a semantic range identical/nearly identical to what I’m sure was the actual semantic range of $\text{N}\bar{\upsilon}\sigma\alpha$, $\nu\acute{\upsilon}\sigma\alpha$, $\nu\acute{\upsilon}\sigma\sigma\omega$, $\nu\acute{\upsilon}\sigma\sigma\alpha$, and the $\nu\upsilon\sigma\sigma\omicron\varsigma$ seen in $\Delta\acute{\iota}\omicron\nu\upsilon\sigma\omicron\varsigma$.

Part 4

From Ancient Greek, the Ancient Greeks and Ancient Greece we now turn our attention to Ancient Italy, the Etruscans and the Etruscan language. Most likely I have discovered the etymology of Etruscan *Pupluns/Fufluns*, who was a god of plant life, happiness, wine, health, and growth in all things. The name surely derives from a root (not exclusive to Etruscan, found also in IE languages and in Non-IE languages not related to or in contact with the Etruscans) *Pup/pop* that meant “to swell out, burgeon, blossom, emerge”: this root probably did not come from a root-meaning of “pointed”, but instead “to swell out, bulge out, puff out”. Maybe instead from a *Pop/pup*=“firm, thick, fat, strong, lively; to grow, to nourish”.

From the same root also derives the name of the ancient Italian/Etruscan city known in Etruscan as *Pupluna, Pufluna* and *Fufluna* and in Latin as *Populonium, Populonia*, and *Populoni*: the name of the city derives from that root most likely because from very ancient times it was a center of viticulture: grape/grapevine-cultivating/growing/harvesting, and wine-making.

The Latin word *populus* (=“people, the public, crowd, host, multitude, nation”) derives from that root-word as well, most likely via Etruscan, and the oldest meaning would have been “crowd, host, multitude”, from the root-meaning described above “to swell out, bulge out, burgeon”. The meaning “army” theorized for Proto-Italic **poplos* derives from “multitude, crowd, host”. The Latin word *populus* (=“poplar tree”), a homonym to the afore-described word, has the same etymology: here, for the poplar tree, the word refers to the great height of the tree, which along with its lateral branches spreading out, was thought of as “burgeoning upwards” from the root-meaning “burgeoning, bulging, swelling, puffing out/up”. Compare the Ancient Greek word for the same tree, αἴγειρος, which derives from αἴγ=“goat”, because goats were symbols (among other things) of great heights, due to the mountain-climbing/mountain-dwelling behavior of goats. See how the word αἴγειρου was used in an Ancient Greek work to describe a high seat in the theatre which had no view of the stage (*Cratin.339*).

Compare also the Latin words *papilla*=“nipple, teat, breast; a rose-bud; a pustule, a pimple”; and *papula*=“a pustule, a pimple”: meanings which all derive from bulging out and bulging up. See also Latin *pupa/puppa*=“little girl, damsel; a doll; a puppet”, *pupus*=“a boy, a child; a puppet, doll”; *pupulus*=“a little boy, a puppet”; *pupillus*=“an orphan boy”; which I argue derive from a nearly identical semantic seen in Ancient Greek νόμφη/νόμφᾶ, except that for the Latin words the root-meaning was probably not “pointed”, but instead “sprouting” deriving from “bulging out” or a similar idea: “pushing out”. From the same sonic-semantic reflexes derive English “pup”=“a young animal” (and by transference, informally, a human child), “puppy/puppie”, and English “pop” in the onomatopoeic sense of imitating the sound of something that bursts (be it a bubble or whatever the case), and bursting proceeds from “swelling out, bulging out”. So Etruscan Pup- seen in Pupluns and Pupluna does not represent something foreign or some complex fantasy that some other linguists may imagine: Etruscan Pupluns most likely derives from a sonic-semantic reflex occurring in very many languages of the world. In Armenian, *p’ap’uk* means “soft, tender, delicate, gentle”: no doubt deriving from the same kind of origin as Latin *pupa/puppa*. In Etruscan Pupluns, Pup=burgeoning, blossoming, emerging, which fits exactly the nature of the god Pupluns among the Etruscans: a god of plant life, happiness, wine, health, and growth in all things.

The Latin word *poples* since it originally referred to the inside hollow of the knee, the ham, the hough, the hock of the knee, only later sometimes used as a word for the knee, very likely does not derive from PIE **k^wék^wlos*, **k^wék^wlom* (=“wheel, circle”, since the knee joint can rotate a lot: compare Spanish *rodilla*, “knee”, from *roda*, “wheel”) but instead because the hollow/underside of the knee is soft and tender, very much so. And the semantic also recalls the “hollow between the lower lip and the chin”/“niche”, two of the meanings of νόμφη/νόμφᾶ.

A.G., 2024